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Instructor: Dr. Hannah Frank

***The Contributing Conditionality of Spillover
of the Civil Wars***
Co-variational analysis

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Declaration of originality

I hereby declare that I have written this seminar paper on my own, have not used any sources or aids other than those specified, and have marked the passages taken from them as such. All aids used are listed in the table below. Regarding the use of Large Language Models (LLM, e.g., Chat-GPT), I have archived the entire LLM interaction history with reference to the submitted work and can present it upon request. This seminar paper has not been presented in this or a similar form in any other course.

Name of aid	Purpose
ChatGPT	All references have been requested to be put into alphabetical order and standardized to APA 7 citation style with consistent interpunction and capitalization.
Chat GPT	In the Case selection subchapter, I needed to rephrase the paragraph since I thought it was not very fluent and reader might have problem understanding it.
	https://chatgpt.com/share/698339e3-2a18-800f-9ce2-b2a46e3b4b17
Grammarly	Spelling and syntax changes

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Introduction

Civil war is a highly complex phenomenon. Even though many studies explain the emergence of the civil war, there is no single holy truth that explains why it emerges. Indeed, some conditions are necessary, and some are sufficient. Yet, certain conditions increase the risk of civil war onset. One such contributing condition is the spillover effect of civil wars into neighbouring countries. This, however, does not automatically mean that once there is a civil war in a state, there will be civil war in the state next to it. Forsberg (2016) theorizes the conditions and likelihood of the spillover. In general, spillover is moderated by the state's capacity to absorb it. Aiming to validate the theory, I am using the refined most similar case design, with two cases exposed to the same external shock (the Rwanda civil war) – Democratic Republic of Congo/Zaire and Tanzania - and differing in state capacity, allowing me to treat state capacity as a moderator, while introducing a contextual reference case to validate the second point of Forsber (2016), that spillover is more likely in states with similar structural conditions. To validate and improve the internal validity of the theory, I ask a research question: *Why are civil wars contagious in some cases but not in others?* and introduce a probabilistic (conditional) hypothesis: Among states neighbouring a civil war and exposed to the same external shock, those with lower state capacity (a contributing condition) are more likely to experience conflict spillover and subsequent civil war onset than neighbouring states with higher state capacity.

The grievances as a cause of civil war, as theorized by Cunningham and Lemke (2014), are present in the DRC case. Even though the political exclusion is present in the DRC case, I argue that Forsberg's (2016) causal claims are strongly proved and supported in this research, for two main reasons: (1) The spillover is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition or a precondition for civil war. It is treated as a contributing condition that increases the risk of diffusion. This has been proven in this analysis. And (2) it is important to distinguish whether there is a real causal link between wars or whether it is rather that neighboring states share similar structural conditions that contribute to conflict (e.g., similar regime types or economic levels in the region, level of democratization, as noted by Gleditsch and Ward, 2000; O'Loughlin et al., 1998; Ward, 2005). Therefore, I conclude that the hypothesis was supported in this most similar case design.

Literature Review

The literature broadly agrees that there are several causes of civil war. The two main explanatory factors for the onset of civil war are grievances and opportunities. Firstly, the argument of grievance has been improved over the year. Generally, moving from Gurr (1974), the relative deprivation J-Curved argumentation¹ and frustration-aggression hypothesis argues that frustration leads to aggression (Dollard et al., 1939). Dollard et al.'s model has been revised by Berkowitz (1989), who introduced the cognitive-neoassociationistic model, arguing that, rather than frustration, the negative experience is the key driver of aggression. Research then moved towards the linkage between cultural differences between and within states and conflicts (Huntington & Jervis, 1997). Posner (2004) argued that there are more cultural differences than actual conflicts; therefore, those differences cannot be mere causes. Later, the ethnic diversity, after new data has been introduced, Cederman et al. (2010) reconceptualized the grievances argument, arguing that not ethnic diversification causes civil war, but political exclusion is the main cause. Citizens want to be governed by representatives from the same ethnic group. Østby (2013) empirically proved that all possible relationships exist between economic inequality and political conflict, which led to the reconceptualization of inequality from vertical towards horizontal inequalities (Stewart, 2016). However, the opportunistic explanations argue, that grievances are present in every society and civil wars are not, therefore arguing that grievances are a necessary condition, yet not sufficient for civil war onset. Opportunity argument, on the other hand, stands on the principle of greed – conflicts provide opportunities to increase the individual utility (Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). Simply, engagement in violent activities is merely an economic activity. Therefore, civil wars are more likely in states with lower GDP, lower incomes, and more natural resources. Fearon and Laitin (2003) argue that GDP can be understood as an indicator of state capacity, as their analysis fails to show the impact of primary commodity exports or secondary education levels. Collier and Hoeffler (2004), on the other hand, use GDP as a proxy for opportunity costs and find a negative correlation between GDP per capita, male secondary education, and economic growth, and the probability of conflict.

Brown's (1996) concept of "bad neighborhood" explains why internal conflicts are more likely in specific regional settings and are not simply the result of domestic factors. States located in conflict regions are more prone to a higher risk of civil war because of the transnational

¹ See Figure 2, Annex

attributes of it. Forsberg (2016) argues that civil wars spill through mechanisms such as refugee flows, the movement of armed groups, arms smuggling, weakened border controls, or interventions by neighboring states motivated by security or strategic interests. The "bad neighbourhood" can reduce the costs of insurgency and weaken state authority even in cases where grievances already exist. These "neighborhood" effects, however, are not in themselves sufficient conditions for civil war onset, but interact with internal vulnerabilities (e.g., low state capacity, political exclusion, weak institutions).

The debate over the civil war onset has been evolving since its introduction, and a deeper understanding of its causes yields more precise predictions. Despite the extensive literature on spatial clustering and transnational dimensions of civil wars (Buhaug & Gleditsch, 2008; Forsberg, 2016), it remains less clear under what domestic conditions the same external shock translates into escalation in the host state. This article contributes to this by conducting a controlled small-N covariational analysis of two exposed neighbors in a most-similar cases design (Lijphart, 1971), examining state capacity as a conditioning factor/contributing condition of spillover.

Theoretical Framework and Causal Mechanism

Forsberg (2016) points out that civil wars tend to cluster spatially and should not be treated as isolated events. If there is conflict in a neighboring country, the likelihood of civil war breaking out in a given state also increases. This "neighborhood effect" has been repeatedly confirmed by quantitative studies (e.g., Buhaug and Gleditsch, 2008; Gleditsch, 2007; Ward and Gleditsch, 2002) and is often captured through the image of "bad neighborhoods" (Brown, 1996). At the same time, however, she emphasizes that it is not enough to simply note the spatial proximity of conflicts. Analytically, it is important to distinguish whether there is a real causal link between wars or whether it is rather that neighboring states share similar structural conditions that contribute to conflict (e.g., similar regime types or economic levels in the region, level of democratization, as noted by Gleditsch and Ward, 2000; O'Loughlin et al., 1998; Ward, 2005).

To explain the concept of spillover, Forsberg (2016) uses the term contagion, i.e., a situation where conflict in state A increases the likelihood of subsequent conflict in state B. She divides this transmission into tangible and intangible mechanisms. Tangible mechanisms include,

in particular, refugee flows, which can increase pressure on the host state and increase existing tensions (Lischer, 2005; Salehyan and Gleditsch, 2006; Salehyan, 2007). The spread of weapons and mobilization of troops, especially in situations of weak border control, has a similar effect, as does regional economic damage, which weakens the state and worsens socio-economic conditions (Murdoch & Sandler, 2002, 2004). The nature of borders and their "permeability" are also important. Moreover, whether the conflict occurs directly on the border also yields significant results (Phillips, 2015). Intangible mechanisms are more ideological and strategic. Conflict can create demonstration effects and encourage learning among actors who adopt tactics or expectations of success from insurgents in neighboring countries (Bakke, 2013; Elkins and Simmons, 2005). This often takes place through transnational ethnic ties that facilitate mobilization, solidarity, or logistical support across borders (Buhaug and Gleditsch, 2008; Forsberg, 2008; Gleditsch, 2007).

In my theoretical approach, it is crucial that Forsberg (2016) does not treat spillover as automatic. She emphasizes the susceptibility to contagion: the same regional shock may cause escalation in one neighbouring state but not in another, because the degree of internal vulnerability and the risk of conflict are decisive. She cites state capacity as a key moderator. States with higher capacity are less susceptible to civil war spillover because they are better able to maintain order, limit escalation, and create protective barriers (Braithwaite, 2010). In the logic of this synthesis, therefore, the weak state capacity of a neighbouring state is a key conditioning factor. With similar external shocks (refugees, weapons, economic losses, etc.), spillover is more likely in states that are unable to control their borders, manage distribution conflicts, and/or quickly suppress armed mobilization.

FIGURE 1: Causal mechanism of spillover effect (based on theoretical assumptions by Forsberg, 2016)

Based on the previous research, the task of this research is to validate the theory using the following hypothesis:

H: Among states neighbouring a civil war and exposed to the same external shock, those with lower state capacity (understood as a contributing condition) are more likely to experience conflict spillover and subsequent civil war onset than neighbouring states with higher state capacity.

Research Design

Methodology

Using the refined most similar case design, with cases exposed to the same external shock (the Rwanda civil war) and differing in state capacity, allows me to treat state capacity as a moderator. The aim of this design is to approximate a controlled comparison in small-N research while holding confounders constant across the cases (Lijphart, 1971). This research

design (covariational analysis) increases internal validity by selecting two cases that are similar in key structural characteristics - regional exposure, low income levels, and significant refugee flows - but differ in the theoretically key conditioning variable, state capacity. At the same time, variation in the level of political exclusion – high in the case of the DRC and significantly lower in Tanzania – is explicitly taken into account, as political exclusion is a separate and established predictor of civil war (Cederman, Wimmer and Min, 2010). This analysis allows me to examine whether spillover effects translate into the outbreak of armed conflict under conditions of low state capacity, understood as a contributing condition, rather than a deterministic cause, while also reflecting that higher levels of political exclusion further increase the underlying risk of conflict, in line with the conditional logic formulated in Forsberg (2016).

Case Selection

Even though civil wars occurred after the Rwandan Civil War in three of Rwanda's four neighbouring states: Burundi (1991–2008), Uganda (1996–1999), and the Democratic Republic of Congo (then Zaire) (1996–1998). Tanzania experienced only one civil war in 2020 according to UCDP data. Given the scope and length of this paper, I focus only on the DRC (Zaire) and Tanzania. This selection is justified for two reasons. First, these cases provide a solid basis for assessing the internal validity of Forsberg's (2016) spillover argument. Second, including Burundi and Uganda would introduce dependence among observations and would yield biased results, because conflict is expected to cluster spatially: Rwanda's neighbours are also neighbours of one another, which complicates identification of spillover pathways and undermines the methodological logic of a straightforward neighbour-based design. By focusing on Tanzania and the DRC, it is possible to better control for potential spillover effects originating from Burundi and Uganda, as both countries border each of the selected cases. At the same time, Tanzania and the DRC are themselves neighbouring states, making it plausible that spillover dynamics may also operate between them.

Independent Variable

The independent variable is the presence of civil war in a neighbouring state. It is operationalized as a dichotomous indicator capturing whether at least one neighbouring country is experiencing a civil war.

However, for further research, to increase the robustness of the measurement and increase internal validity, it might be useful to transform the independent variable into continuous, depending on whether other neighbouring states have experienced the civil war within the time given to capture the effect of “bad neighbourhoods” as Brown (1996) introduced.

For my case study, the independent variable remains binary, meaning the neighbouring country did or did not experience civil war. I am focusing on the case of the Rwanda Civil War as a case of departure, where civil war, according to the UCDP dataset (Davies et al., 2025; Harbom et al., 2008), lasted from October 1990 until 1994, and then from 12th June 1996 until 2000.

Dependent variable

The dependent variable of this study is the occurrence of civil war in a neighbouring state after the outbreak of the Rwandan civil war, i.e., conflict spillover. The variable is operationalized as a dichotomous indicator indicating whether a civil war occurred in a neighbouring state after the start of the Rwandan civil war. Analytically, the dependent variable is not solely conceived as the result of spillover, since that is treated as a contributing condition. This means that the civil war in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (then Zaire) and the absence of such a war in Tanzania are interpreted, in relation to the Rwandan conflict, as external shocks, while highlighting the contextual similarities with the state of nature of the spillover. This approach is consistent with Forsberg's (2016) theoretical framework, which views spillover as a probabilistic process dependent on the receiving state's internal characteristics.

The dependent variable is therefore closely linked to the moderating role of state capacity. High state capacity reduces the likelihood that transnational impulses (such as refugee flows, the spread of weapons, armed actors, or demonstration effects) will escalate into organised domestic violence. Conversely, low state capacity increases the state's vulnerability to civil war diffusion, thereby increasing the probability of a positive outcome for the dependent variable.

Moderating Variable

Regarding the moderating variable, state capacity, I use the Quality of Government dataset (Teorell et al., 2025), especially the State Capacity Index measurement by O'Reilly and Murphy (2022). “Unlike narrower measures of fiscal capacity or legal capacity, the index

is more comprehensive, using data from the Varieties of Democracy dataset on fiscal capacity, a state's control over its territory, the rule of law, and the provision of public goods used to support markets. Like the previous studies, the results derived from the State Capacity Index demonstrate that the historical prevalence of warfare predicts state capacity.” (cited as authors' request from O'Reilly and Murphy 2022). This measure offers a comparatively comprehensive and precise operationalization for the present analysis. For DRC, I lag the measure by one year relative to conflict onset ($t-1$), in 1995, and for Tanzania, the same year.

Control Variables

The academic literature agrees on several structural conditions that systematically increase a state's vulnerability to civil war. Cunningham and Lemke (2014, p. 330) point out that civil wars are more likely in states with low average incomes, in regimes that are neither fully democratic nor fully autocratic, in countries neighboring states in civil war, and in states that have had recent experience with civil war. Brown (1996) similarly argues that states in so-called “bad neighborhoods” face a higher baseline risk of conflict. This argument is followed by Forsberg (2016), who shows that refugee inflows can increase the likelihood of civil war in host countries, but this effect is conditional: state capacity is a key moderator, determining whether external shocks translate into internal violence. Cederman, Wimmer and Min (2010) further emphasize that conflict risk is not primarily related to ethnic diversity per se, but to the political exclusion of ethnic groups from power. In line with these theoretical expectations, the summary table focuses on control variables that are largely comparable across cases - low income levels, exposure to conflict in a neighboring state, high refugee flows, regime character, and levels of political exclusion - while specifically highlighting state capacity as a key moderating variable.

Findings

For easy visualization of the differences, please see the most-similar cases design summary table (Table 1) below. The table also includes Rwanda as a contextual reference case, allowing a comparison of structural conditions across all three analyzed states and highlighting Forsberg (2016) 's argument that spillover is more likely among neighbours with similar structural conditions.

For the empirical part and data collection, several datasets have been used. Firstly, for the key moderating variable, the State Capacity Index for DRC is -2.89; Tanzania is 1.0; and Rwanda, as a comparative case, is 0.21. Refugees' inflow data has been retrieved from the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees report. During the most violent phase of the Rwandan genocide in 1994, the situation changed dramatically: more than 2.3 million refugees left Rwanda, heading mainly to the Democratic Republic of the Congo (1.4 million), Tanzania (674,000), and Burundi (260,000)². For control variables, the data for regime type and political exclusion index are from the Varieties of Democracy Dataset (V-Dem). Regime type is derived from V-Dem Democracy Indices. Moreover, DCR was a fully autocratic regime in 1995, and Tanzania was a dominant-party regime, where, even though there were free elections in 1993, the ruling party stayed in an absolutely dominant position. Exclusion by Political Group Index is operationalized as "when individuals are denied access to services or participation in governed spaces based on their identity or belonging to a particular group" (Pemstein et al., 2025, p. 308). DRC has an index of 0.853; Tanzania, 0.475; and Rwanda, 0.813. The GDP data are from the World Bank Dataset. DCR had a GDP per capita of \$127 in 1995; Tanzania had a GDP per capita of \$258.4; and Rwanda had a GDP per capita of \$228. Therefore, all are relatively similar compared to the rest of the world (World Bank, n.d.).

² For graphical presentation, please see Figure 3, Appendix

Table 1: Most-similar case selection - Variation between DRC and Tanzania, including Rwanda for structural conditions comparison – contextual reference case (based on the theoretical framework by Forsberg, 2016)

Case	Civil War in Neighbouring State (X)	State Capacity (Moderator)	Civil War Onset/ Spillover (Y)	Refugees Inflow	GDP per Capita	Regime Type	Political Exclusion Index
DRC/Zaire 1995	Yes	Low	? (Yes)	<i>High</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Autocracy</i>	<i>High</i>
Tanzania 1995	Yes	Medium	? (No)	<i>High</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Semi-Autocracy</i>	<i>Medium</i>
Rwanda 1995 (Contextual Reference Case)					<i>Low</i>	<i>Autocracy</i>	<i>High</i>

Conclusion

The analysis highlights the conditional nature of spillover effects on civil wars. The case comparison of DRC and Tanzania shows that exposure to external conflict and high refugee flows alone is not a sufficient condition for the outbreak of civil war. These findings support Forsberg's (2016) theoretical approaches, which emphasize the importance of the state's domestic absorptive capacities in mediating transnational pressures.

Grievance factors as causes of civil war in the sense of Cunningham and Lemke (2014) are present in the case of DRC, especially in the form of political exclusion, but the results also strongly support Forsberg's (2016) argument, as spillover appears to be a contributing (not necessary nor sufficient) condition that increases the risk of conflict spreading. At the same time, the analysis emphasizes the need to distinguish the true causal link between wars from spatial clustering caused by shared structural characteristics of neighbouring states. Finally, it can be concluded that the hypothesis was supported within the most similar cases design.

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Annex

Figure 1: Gurr's relative deprivation and revolution

FIGURE 1. NEED SATISFACTION AND REVOLUTION

Source: Gurr (1974)

Figure 3: Forced displacement of the Rwanda population

Source: U.N. High Commissioner for Refugees (n.d.)